

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OKOYE****FIRST NAME: IJEOMA****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA 401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401 RP6

1. Is it feasible to have a thesis completed with a futuristic input without the need for further research by another researcher?
 - This is not feasible considering the future cannot be clearly predicted.
 - This is feasible if the researcher takes an analytical approach with predictability of the future.¹**
 - This might make the research area stiff and unyielding to changes in the future.
 - The research work might not need future inputs if it majors on a minor unchanging area.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition- (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 11.

2. Can wrong punctuation derail the viewpoint of a research work?
- The punctuation gives the meaning of a work its correct body structure and conclusion.²**
 - A person can still discern the meaning if the punctuations are not placed correctly.
 - The words written are more important than the punctuation.
 - The punctuations are mere necessities and do not affect the work.
3. Can a major life activity be researched or should research only be academically based?
- Short of been too serious and overtly cautious, they shouldn't be researched.
 - The risk of stiffness in life can occur.
 - Major life-changing activities should be researched on a lighter note before being embarked upon.³**
 - The joy of the activity is removed with this restriction.
4. Will reporting personal view affect how a work is accepted?
- A personal view presented in an impersonal way they cover fully data been disseminated should be accepted.⁴**
 - People don't always respond well to changes.
 - A personal view can border on selfishness.

² Ibid., 17.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis and Dissertation*. Ninth Edition- (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018) 19.

⁴ Ibid., 136.

- The work will be limited to very few audiences who can relate to the personal view.
5. Will there be an opening someday for researchers to cite themselves under the bibliography?
- A person can still discern the meaning if the punctuations are not placed correctly.
 - The words written are more important than the punctuation.
 - The punctuation is a mere necessity and does not affect the work.
 - The punctuation gives the meaning of a work its correct body structure and conclusion.⁵**
6. Does “style” prevent more audience for researchers?
- It reduces number of audience.
 - Research works might have incurred majorly scholarly audience.
 - It takes the novelty and puts stiff seriousness in research works.
 - The audience might need to acquire a little knowledge of research work before taking it up to enable an understanding body of research.⁶**
7. Are research works rigid and audience-selective?

⁵ Ibid., 370.

⁶ Ibid., 332.

- The target audience is reached on a scholarly scale, but maybe -flexibility would yield more audience.⁷**
- The rigid detailing of a research work hinders non-scholarly audiences.
- Information that helps in serious life-changing decisions does not get to everyday people.
- The rigidity and stiffness can be discouraging to a non-scholarly audience.

8. How does plagiarism get detected?

- It may not be seen because of the number of referenced works used.
- A well-versed scholarly lecturer can detect plagiarism.⁸**
- A reduced number of referenced works gives room for more attention to research work.
- This may need to depend on the ethics of the researcher.

9. How can tertiary sources be accepted?

- Non acceptance prevents unchecked information been used.
- If they can provide original insight analyses.
- If the author is well known.⁹**
- If the researcher has maximized primary sources.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition- (California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 102.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis and Dissertation*. Ninth Edition, 370.

⁹ Ibid., 37.

10. How can research works been read gain more audience?

- Less rigid approach to body of the work.**¹⁰
- More accessibility online.
- Reduced emphasis and dependency on primary sources.
- Widen writing scope to include the forecasted future.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 102.